

Research Article

**Organoleptic Analysis of Pounded Yam Prepared from a Yam Pounder
Designed and Fabricated in Nigeria**

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Abstract

A delicacy eaten by Nigerians is pounded yam eaten with any form of soup. It is prepared manually by pounding yam and cocoyam with mortar and pestle. It takes 30-45 mins to plan. Efforts are directed towards reducing the heavy pressure on the preparation of the pounded yam. The design and manufacture of pounding machines by the Department of Engineering, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Nigeria, is one of the efforts. The object of this research was to conduct an organoleptic analysis of the pounded yam developed from the manufactured machine. In order to assess the organoleptic analysis of pounded yam in terms of appearance, taste, color, odor and texture, a ten-man panelist was used. A quality class of 22.6-25.0 (excellent), 20.2-22.5 (good), 18.2-20.1 (satisfactory), 16.2-18.1 (less satisfactory) and <15.2.5 (less satisfactory) were scored by the panelists (unsatisfactory). Sensory characteristics were also graded as 1= unsatisfactory, 2= less satisfying, 3= satisfactory, 4= good, and 5= excellent. The findings showed that the mean results were 4.55, 4.43, 4.15, 4.32, and 4.08 respectively for color, colour, odour, taste, and texture. Variation coefficients (per cent) were 16.89, 17.80, 21.65, 15.67, and 24.40. The skewness of the parameters was negative, although its Kurtosis has only odor in negative form (-0.37). The presence (19-24 percent) of all samples was ranked high above all other parameters by all the panelists. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient and Principal Component Analysis revealed the parameter relationships. In conclusion, the machine pounded with yam was scored above satisfactory, which means that the machine produced was effective.

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Keywords: Pounded yam, cocoyam, machine, panelist, texture, Yorubas, Nigeria

Introduction

Africans are blessed with local foods, and one of the countries in Nigeria is also blessed with various kinds of local foods. Pounded yam, a very popular delicacy, is one of the local dishes (Olaoye and Oyewole, 2012). With distinct soups such as vegetables, ogbono, okro, egunsi soups, pounded yam is eaten. In southwest Nigeria, pounded yam serves as a menu for most occasions and parties. Pounded yam is typically made with mortar and pestle from yam, cocoyam or the mixtures, and pound.

Yam, a pounded yam ingredient, is a member of the Dioscorea genus, an essential staple food in West Africa (Ekwu et al., 2005). It is cultivated in Africa, the Americas, the Caribbean, the South Pacific and Asia on an annual and perennial basis. It is native to Western Africa (IITA, 2018). The yellow yam (*D. cayenensis*), water yam (*D. alata*), *D. rotundata*. Uh. Esculenta. Yam has a strong prospect of helping to close the expected food deficit in Africa in the 21st century, according to FAO (1989). Nigeria single handedly generates 71 percent of the 94 percent of West African production, making a total of over 37 million tons (IITAA) (2018). Tubers are planted and harvested for 180 to 270 days in Nigeria in February and April. Yam tubers are nutritionally made up of about 21% dietary fiber and are rich in carbohydrates, vitamin C and essential minerals. Yams are processed through a drying phase into less perishable goods to produce flour (Jimoh and Olatidoye, 2009).

Cocoyams, which belong to the Araceae family, are perennial plants. This is an edible root and vegetable crop (Deni, 2000). Cocoyams that are planted as food crops belong either to the Colocasia genus or to the Xanthosoma genus and are composed of a large spherical corm from which several large leaves emerge. The species of Colocasia may also be referred to as taro and comes from Southeast or Central Asia (Rao et al., 2010). Cocoyam, as compared to cassava and yam, has high nutritional values (vitamins, minerals, and protein). Roasting, boiling, frying, baking, pounding and milling may be eaten in various ways. Colocasia species are considered to have health benefits, such as reducing symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis, cancer prevention, reducing blood pressure, playing essential roles in the immune system, reducing cramps, boosting vision and improving learning (Admin, 2016).

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Production of pounded yam is a tedious process that is carried out by pounding cooked yam slices in mortar and pestle to a smooth consistency of the dough (Oluwamukomi and Adeyemi, 2015). To remove the repetitive operation, there are a lot of changes in the processing of pounded yam. Pounded yam flour has been made, for instance, this is just fortified flour, which is ready to be served in a pot within 5-10 minutes (Olaoye and Oyewole, 2012; Ayodeji et al., 2012; Adeola et al., 2012; Oluwamukomi and Adeyemi, 2015). Also, the design and manufacture of machines used in the development of pounded yam is also (Adebayo et al., 2014; Ikechukwu and Munch, 2015). These and some others, however, failed because of some limitations, such as poor pounding, restricted quantity production, problems with the stirrer or mixer, and excessive heat production during use, just to name a few. The pounding machine used in the study was planned and fabricated on this basis to correct the limitations. The organoleptic analysis of the pounded yam developed from the machine is part of the evaluation, so this research evaluated the acceptability, taste, odor, color, and texture using a ten-man panelist.

Materials and Methods

From the Oja Oba market in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, the tubers of white yam (*Dioscorea alata*) and white cocoyam corms (*Colocasia esculenta*) varieties, the gas cooker, pestle and mortar used for this work were procured.

Design and Fabrication of Machine

The design and fabrication (Figure 1) were carried out in the workshop of the Department of Agricultural and Bio-Environmental Engineering, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, and have been reported elsewhere (Adigun, 2015).

Figure 1. Design and Fabrication of Machine

Preparation of Yam tuber and corms of cocoyam for pounding

1. Cocoyam only pounded with mortar and pestle - 910g (Control)
2. Yam only pounded with mortar and pestle - 910g (Control)
3. A mixture of yam (637g) and cocoyam (273g) - Ratio 3:1
4. A mixture of yam (455g) and cocoyam (455g) - Ratio 1:1
5. Cocoyam only pounded with the machine - 910g
6. Yam only pounded with the machine - 910g

Control

Same quantities were used in the preparations, but mortar and pestles were employed in pounding (Figure 2)

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Figure 2. Pounded yam made of mortar and pestle

Measurements (Time and volumes)

The volume of water used for cooking - 500cm^3 (Enough to cover the yam and cocoyam)

Time of cooking - 12 min (The yam and cocoyam were cut into small pieces).

Time of pounding (Machine) - 3mins

Time of pounding (Control) - 10 mins

Production of Pounded Yam

Cooking of yam

The tubers and combs of the brown outer layer were peeled, sliced, washed with plenty of clean water, and cooked for twelve minutes with water, and then checked by piercing with a kitchen fork to see if the yams were soft enough for the pounding. The Pounding Flow Chart is shown in Figure 3.

Pounded yam preparations and Cocoyam

The cooked yam was transferred, coated and switched on to the machine. There was a 3-minute rotation of the system rotor. The pounded yam was ready after this time, packed into a clean plate, held hot, and then served to the panelists (Figure 4). For the power, the same pounding procedure was used, but this time the fabricated system was replaced by a pestle and mortar until the yam was seedless and can easily be molded (20 minutes).

Note

The yam used for the project remained for more than three months prior to use. New yams may not be suitable for pounding purposes.

Figure 3: Flow Chart of the Production of Pounded Yam

Sensory Assessment

They compared the pounded yam made of yam, cocoyam and the mixtures of both. From the students and staff of the Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State, two separate groups (10 members; 5 men and 5 women) of untrained sensory panelists were chosen. They were educated in the methodologies involved briefly.

A separate score sheet was supplied to each panelist. Between two tasting sessions, water was given to rinse the dish. Quality characteristics, colour, texture, taste, appearance, and odour were also assessed. Quality grading classes: 22.6-25.0 (excellent), 20.2-22.5 (good), 18.2-20.1 (satisfactory), 16.2-18.1 (less satisfactory) and <15.2-22.5 (good), 18.2-20.1 (satisfactory)

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(unsatisfactory). Sensory attributes were also rated as 1= unsatisfactory, 2= less satisfying, 3= satisfying, 4= decent, and 5= outstanding.

Figure 4. Samples of Pounded Yam produced by the fabricated machine and the control

Statistically, Minitab 18 (Descriptive statistical, correlation coefficient, and matrix) and Excel were used to evaluate the findings obtained in the analysis (charts).

Results and Discussion

The descriptive statistical findings of the organoleptic studies of pounded yam samples are described in Table 1. The findings showed that the mean results were 4.55, 4.43, 4.15, 4.32, and 4.08 respectively for color, colour, odour, taste, and texture. Variation coefficients (percent) were 16.89, 17.80, 21.65, 15.67, and 24.40, suggesting that the values of the panelists' judgments showed little variation. It can be inferred that the panelists approved all the sample items. These findings were in line with those published previously (Adeola et al., 2012; Akissoe et al., 2009). The parameters' skewness was in the negative. This showed that the mean is less than the median, which is always less than the mode, in the distributions. If it were to be distributed positively, the inverse is the case. If it is skewed to a normal distribution, one of the tails is longer than the other. It implies that they have long tails in the negative

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directions, because the distributions are negatively biased. In negative type, Only odour has its Kurtosis (-0.37). Since this value is lower than 0, it is called a "light-tailed" value. Kurtosis is calculated against the regular distribution, as it is known. When the kurtosis is close to 0, a regular distribution (mesokurtic distributions) is always assumed, but when it is less than 0, then light tails are distributed (platykurtic distribution). If the kurtosis is greater than zero, so there are heavier tails in the distribution and a leptokurtic distribution is called (McNeese, 2016).

The individual score of the panelists depicted in Figure 5 showed that, with the exception of the color and texture they rated good, panelists 5 and 6 rated almost all products excellent. The panelists accepted products 5 (Cocoyam only pounded by a machine) and 6 (Yam only pounded by a machine). The manufactured system could have enhanced the pounded yam's sensory efficiency. The contribution of each organoleptic parameter in the samples was shown in Figure 6. The presence (19-24 percent) of all samples was ranked high above all other parameters by all the panelists. There were no signs of unmashed yam or soil that may have altered the appearance. The appearance was not affected by stain from the machine and mortar and pestle. In marketing and preference, the outstanding presence in the samples will benefit. Colour contributed 19-22%, due to the taster status of panelists and their diverse views, the reasons for the discrepancies were (perceived colour differently). The odor was also scored at between 12 and 24 percent. Odour can be a food intake appetizer and an essential food feature that affects the behaviour of food choice. The panelist's reported odour indicated that the pounded yam collected using the machine was satisfactory. In comparison with a commercial pouno yam developed by Adeola et al. (2012), the results obtained in his analysis were pounded yam (Akissoe et al., 2009; Adeyeye and Oluwatola, 2014; Otegbayo et al., 2007; 'foutou' (Nindjin et al., 2007) in terms of sensory characteristics.

Table 3 displays the Pearson correlation coefficient analysis of the determined organoleptic parameters. The correlation summary was provided in this table. Significant associations were observed between odor and color ($r=0.46$), taste and odor ($r=0.51$), odor and texture ($r=0.52$), and taste and texture ($r=0.54$). Other good associations were the association between odour and colour was weak. This meant that all the organoleptic parameters used in the test gave both the control and the test a clear account of the pounded yam samples (machine). The findings of the evaluations were similar to those of pounded yam and composite pouno yam obtained by Oluwamukomi and Adeyemi (2015) and Baah et al. (2009). The panelists liked the tastes, scent, and color of the samples. The matrix plot of the findings was shown in Figure 7. The plot

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clarified the relationships of the samples in appearance, colour, odour, taste, and texture. The organoleptic experiments were diagonal, with each variable plotted at the top and down against each other (forming mirror image). Where the scatterplot looks identical, a connection is seen. It showed from the table that there were connections between texture, taste and odor; taste and odor, and color and odor. This has been verified by the Pearson correlation coefficient in Table2.

Table 3 displays the effects of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and loadings. The number of principal components (PCs) was determined by a size greater than 0.5 of its own magnitude. There was a clear connection between the PC1 portion and odor and taste. This revealed that there was a connection between smell and taste. The second (PC2) correlation was -0.705 and 0.654, respectively, for appearance and colour. PC1's overall variance percentage was 48.1 percent, PC2 accounted for 66.1 percent, and PC3 had 82.8 percent. The organoleptic parameters were all clustered together in the loading plot (Figure 8), and they were far from the origin, showing that they were correlated. Odor, texture, and taste were closer than any other parameter, indicating a higher correlation, as shown in Table 3.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistical results of organoleptic analysis test

	Appearance	Colour	Odour	Taste	Texture
Mean	4.55	4.43	4.15	4.32	4.08
SE Mean	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.09	0.13
Std Deviation	0.77	0.79	0.90	0.68	1.00
Coef Variation (%)	16.89	17.80	21.65	15.67	24.40
Minimum	1.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	1.00
Maximum	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Skewness	-2.49	-2.02	-0.74	-0.82	-0.92
Kurtosis	8.14	8.14	-0.37	1.02	0.30

Table 2. Pearson Correlation Coefficient of the test results (P-Value)

	Appearance	Colour	Odour	Taste	
Texture					
Appearance	1				
Colour	0.131	1			
Odour	0.271	0.457	1		
Taste	0.214	0.310	0.506	1	
Texture	0.227	0.169	0.516	0.539	1

P<0.05

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Table 3. Principal Component Analysis loading factor of the results

Variable	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5
Appearance	0.293	-0.705	-0.638	0.082	0.053
Colour	0.371	0.654	-0.507	0.080	0.414
Odour	0.537	0.146	-0.034	-0.512	-0.654
Taste	0.505	-0.003	0.318	0.775	-0.209
Texture	0.483	-0.233	0.483	-0.353	0.595
Eigen value	2.405	0.898	0.848	0.475	0.382
Proportion (%)	48.1	18.0	16.8	9.95	7.76
Cumulative (%)	48.1	66.1	82.9	92.4	100.0

(1)- Cocoyam only pounded with mortar and pestle (Control) (2) - Yam only pounded with mortar and pestle (Control) (3) - Mixture of yam and cocoyam (Ratio 3:1). (4) - Mixture of yam and cocoyam (Ratio 1:1). (5)- Cocoyam only pounded with machine (6) - Yam only pounded with machine

Fig 5. The ratings of the samples by individual panelists (1-10)

Fig 6. The contributions of each organoleptic parameter in the samples.

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Fig 7. Matrix plot of the rest results

Fig 8. Loading plot of the organoleptic results

Conclusion

The control (pounded yam from mortar and pestle) and test samples (pounded yam from the manufactured machine) of pounded yam, cocoyam and the mixtures of both were analyzed organoleptically. The analysis showed that the panelists approved all the samples. The findings also showed that the presentation of the pounded yam and

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cocoyam samples was excellent only from the manufactured machine and the control was scored. To conclude, the performance of the fabricated machine was high.

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References

Adebayo A.A., Yusuf K.A., and Oladipo A (2014). Fabrication and Performance Evaluation of a Yam Pounder Cum Boiler. *Scientia Agriculturae*. 8(3): 112-120.

Adeola A.A, Otegbayo B.O., and Ogunnoiki (2012), Preliminary Studies on the Development and Evaluation of Instant Pounded Yam from *Dioscorea alata*. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.* 16(3): 287 – 290.

Adeyeye Samuel Ayofemi and Oluwatola Olatunde Jacob. (2014). Quality Assessment and Acceptability of Pounded Yam from Different Varieties of Yam. *Nat Sci.* 12(4):115-119.

Adigun E.T (2015). Testing and Renovation of yam pounding machine. Department of Agricultural Technology, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State. ND Project. Unpublished.

Akissoe N, Mestres C, Hounhouigan J., and Nago M (2009). Sensory and Physicochemical Quality of Pounded Yam: Varietal and Storage Effects. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation* 33: 75–90.

Admin (2016). The nutritional and health benefits of cocoyam. Food and nutrition. Pharmanews. <https://www.pharmanewsonline.com/8216-2/>.

Ayodeji S.P., Olabanji O.M., and Akinnuli B.O (2014). Development and Performance Evaluation of a Sieving Machine for Pounded Yam Process Plant. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Applied Sciences*. 5(4): 229-236.

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ISSN: 2141 - 4068 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Baah F.D, Maziya-Dixon B, Asiedu R, Oduro I and Ellis W.O (2009). Physicochemical and pasting characterisation of water yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) and relationship with eating quality of pounded yam. *Journal of Food, Agriculture & Environment*. 7(2):107-112.

Deni Bown (2000). *Aroids: Plants of the Arum Family*. Timber Press, Portland.

Ekwu F.C, Ozo N.O, Ikegwu O.J, (2005). Quality of fufu from white yam varieties (*Dioscorea* spp). *Nigerian Food Journal* 23:107-113.

FAO (1989). *Roots, Tubers, and Plantains in Food Security: In Sub-Saharan Africa, in Latin America and the Caribbean, in the Pacific*". FAO. 1989. ISBN 978-92-5-102782-0.

Ikechukwu G.A and Munch M.J (2015). Development of a Motorized Yam Pounding Machine Design to Improve Standard of Living for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria. Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering 2015 Vol II. WCE 2015, July 1 - 3, 2015, London, U.K.

IITA (2018). Yam (*Dioscorea* species). <http://www.iita.org/crops/dioscoria/>. Accessed 1st October, 2018.

Jimoh, K.O. and Olatidoye O.P., (2009). Evaluation of physicochemical and rheological characteristics of soybean fortified yam flour. *Journal of Applied Biosciences* 13:703-706.

Nindjin C., Otokore D., Hauser S., Tschannen A, Farah Z., and Girardin, O. (2007). Determination of relevant sensory properties of pounded yams (*Dioscorea* spp.) using a locally based descriptive analysis methodology. *Food Quality and Preference*. 18(2): 450-459.

McNeese B (2016). Are the Skewness and Kurtosis Useful Statistics? <https://www.spcforexcel.com/knowledge/basic-statistics/are-skewness-and-kurtosis-useful-statistics>. Updated, February 2016.

Olaoye, J. O., and S. N. Oyewole. (2012). Optimization of some "poundo" yam production parameters. *Agric Eng Int: CIGR Journal*, 14(2):58-67.

Oluwamukomi M.O and Adeyemi A.O (2015). Physico-Chemical, Pasting, and Sensory Properties of "Poundo"-Yam Enriched with Defatted Soy Flour. *Applied Tropical Agriculture*. 20(1): 89-95.

Otegbayo, B., Aina, J., Abbey, L., Sakyi-Dawson, E., Bokanga, M. and Asiedu, R. (2007). Texture profile analysis applied to pounded yam. *Journal of Texture Studies*, 38(3): 355-372.

Rao V. R., Matthews P.J, Eyzaguirre P.B and Hunter D (eds) (2010). The Global Diversity of Taro: Ethnobotany and Conservation. Rome, Bioversity International.